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CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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Governor Ganduje Charges CDA-Trained Participants to be Self-Reliant

Kano State Governor, Dr. Abdullahi Umar Ganduje has charged hundreds of youth and women trained by the CDA on agricultural value chains to use the opportunity to become self-reliant so that the society will benefit immensely through poverty reduction and employment generation.

The Governor, who was represented by his Deputy and Chairman of Kano Committee on the APPEALS project, Dr. Nasiru Yusuf Gawuna, at the closing ceremony of the APPEALS training, urged beneficiaries to make good use of the opportunity to become self-employed.

Dr. Gawuna, who was also represented by his Senior Special Assistant on Administration, Dr. Mustapha Yusuf Abubakar congratulated the beneficiaries for being trained by CDA, a renowned Africa centre of excellence in dryland agriculture.

According to Ganduje, the World Bank, in partnership with the Federal Government and state governments earmarked \$200m to empower 60,000 beneficiaries, who are expected to employ about

360,000 people through various agricultural value chains.

The Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, urged the beneficiaries to maximally use the opportunity of the training to develop themselves, hoping that in the next three years, there would be success stories. "Each of you was selected among many people. If you scale through, you will be given support to start-up a business. Whatever you are given is to develop the business you are going to set up and use it for the benefit of yourselves and others," he said.

The Coordinator of the training and Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, CDA, Professor Amina Mustapha, said APPEALS project was implemented in 6 states of the country and CDA was selected by the three states to train its beneficiaries. She expressed gratitude for the opportunity given to the centre and urged the beneficiaries to make judicious use of the resources that would be given to them in order to become employers of labour in the country.

CDA Industry/Sectoral Advisory Board Inaugurated

The Vice Chancellor of Bayero University, Kano, Professor Muhammad Yahuza Bello on Monday, 3rd February, 2020 inaugurated the Industry/Sectoral Advisory Board of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) with Hajjiya Karimatu Ibrahim Babangida, the Director, Federal Department of Agriculture as Chairperson of the Board.

The Vice Chancellor, who was represented by the Deputy Vice Chancellor, Academics, Professor Adamu Idris Tanko, charged the Board members to use their wealth of experience to bear in the Centre's activities and make it more relevant to the local and regional environments.

He expressed optimism that the contribution of the Board would make positive impact to CDA and Bayero University, Kano in general.

Speaking on behalf of the Board members, the Chairperson, Hajjiya Karimatu Babangida, expressed appreciation to the management of Bayero University and CDA for appointing them to steer the affairs of the Board.

According to her, climate change has affected agricultural activities negatively especially in the dryland areas, noting that the areas could turn this challenge into opportunities and become food baskets of the world.

The Chairperson stated that another area that the Board would give priority is entrepreneurship in agriculture, in which students would be well prepared for industries before their graduation so that the existing gap would be bridged.

She emphasized that the Board would do everything within its powers to guide the CDA to achieve its mandate.

Speaking earlier, the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin said the setting up of the board was part of the World Bank's requirement that the activities of the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACEs) must be aligned with the industries.

The Director noted that since the establishment of CDA in 2012, the University Management had wisdom of designing a strategy of linking the activities of the Centre with the industries. He said the CDA was lucky to have such technocrats to be at the helm of its Industry Advisory Board.

Other members of the Board are: Mr. Subramanian Ramasubramanian Balasubramanian, Vice President, International Business Development, Jains Irrigation System, India; Alhaji Aminu Buhari, Director, Capital Agricultural Development Ltd; Alhaji Nasiru Wada, Magajin Garin Kano and Managing Director, Esoterra Investment Ltd; Dr. Lamourdia Cisse, Vice President

OCP Africa, Casablanca, Morocco; Dr Joseph Odusanya, Biocrops Biotechnology Ltd; Alhaji Safiyanu Madugu, Managing Director/CEO, Dala Foods Nigeria Ltd; Mohammed Salasi Idris, Country Representative, IFDC; Professor Sani Miko, Country Director, Sasakawa Africa Association; Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, Director CDA (Secretary); Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, Deputy Director, Training, CDA, Professor Amina Mustapha, Deputy Director, Publications and Outreach, CDA and Dr. Kabir Mustapha, Deputy Director Research, CDA, who will serve as assistant secretaries.

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CDA Participates at 3rd ACE Impact & 12th ACE I Workshop

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The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) participated in the 3rd ACE Impact and 12th ACEI Workshop held at Sheraton Hotel, Abuja, Nigeria between 24th and 28th February, 2020.

The workshop was attended by 54 Centres of Excellence across 12 countries from West and Central Africa. Nigeria had 20 Centres of Excellence in attendance, with 10 in ACE 1 and other 10 in the ACE Project.

Bayero University, Kano was among the few Universities with two Centres of Excellence, the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (ACEDA) and the African Centre of Excellence in Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP).

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin M. Jibrin, Deputy Director, Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Professor Amina Mustapha and Coordinator Training, Dr Yusuf Garba, represented the CDA at the three-day workshop.

The opening session was facilitated by the ACE Impact Project Manager, Dr. Sylvia C. Mkandawire.

Welcome address at the occasion was delivered by Professor Etienne Ehile, the AAU Secretary General, while Professor Leopoldo Amado (ECOWAS Commissioner), Professor A.A. Rasheed (Executive Secretary, NUC), Kathleen Whimp (Operations Manager, WB Nigeria) and Andre Hue (Deputy Director, AFD) delivered the opening remarks.

The formal launch of the workshop was done by the Honourable Minister of State for Education, Dr. Chukuemaka Nwajiuba, who was represented by the Permanent Secretary in the Ministry.

After the opening session, the Nigeria's Coordinator of ACE Project, Dr. Joshua Atah, facilitated the session on End of Project Report, which highlighted Key Achievements and Consolidation of Lessons learnt from the ACE1. In this session, Mrs Adeline Addy presented Aggregate M&E Results Progress while Mrs Himdat Bayusuf (ACE 1 and ACE

Impact 1 Team Leader and ACE IMPACT II Co-Team Leader) made presentation on Disbursement and Fund Utilization by the ACEs.

Professor Jonathan Mba, the ACE 1 Project Coordinator at the AAU presented the End of Project Completion Report.

The objectives of these presentations were to inform existing Centres on their performance and provide new centres with an overview of some key milestones and results expected of them.

Plenary presentations on ACE Impact Overview and Update was made by Dr. Sylvia C. Mkwandawire and Dr. Ekua Bentel (ACE IMPACT II Team Leader and Co-Team Leader ACE IMPACT). Update on AFD supported countries was presented by Dr. Quentin Delpech of French Development Agency. Keynote address as presented by Douglas Blackson on international accreditation of Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education.

The objective was to drill down into the practical needs and current good practice for international accreditation in higher education. The session was facilitated by Dr. Muhammed Salifu (PSC Member, Ghana).

Parallel sessions on revenue generation, internships, entrepreneurship and innovation and institutional impact followed the plenary session.

The objective of these parallel sessions was to share experiences on revenue generation, internships, entrepreneurship and innovation as well as share global best practices. Prof J. M. Jibrin of the Centre for Dryland Agriculture was among the panellists for internships. A Welcome Dinner was organized by the government of Nigeria in honour of the workshop and held at Central Park, Abuja.

Other Plenary and parallel sessions on Institutional Impact, verification, thematic breakout sessions and M&E clinics took place in the remaining two days. The workshop ended on Friday 28th February with a closing ceremony at NUC. There were presentations on feedback from thematic breakout session and key next steps by Prof. J. Mbah and Dr S. C. Mkwandawire.

Closing remarks were presented by the Prof. A.A. Rasheed (Executive Secretary, NUC) and Shubham Chaud (representative of World Bank, Nigeria Office). The workshop was officially declared closed by the Minister of State for Education, Dr. Chukuemaka Nwajiuba.

APPEALS Commends CDA for Training 1400 Youth, Women on Agric Value Chains

The National Project Coordinator of APPEALS Dr. Aminu Babandi, has heaped praises on the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) for training youth and women on agricultural value chains so as to be self reliant.

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on Saturday, 18th January, 2020 completed the training of 1400 youth and women from Kano, Kaduna and Kogi states under the World Bank's project of Agro-Processing Productivity Enhancement and Livelihood Improvement Support Project (APPEALS).

The participants were trained on rice, fisheries and poultry value chains through intensive skills acquisition, practical and field trips that exposed them to learn activities of the various chains. The training was aimed at creating job opportunities, providing unemployment and eradicating poverty among youth and women.

The Coordinator of the APPEALS, said the Centre had demonstrated its competence, resilience and professionalism by using hands-on methods to train the participants, saying that no doubt it deserved to be called a centre of excellence.

The National Coordinator, who was represented by Dr. Salisu Garba, explained that the project provided the opportunity for beneficiaries to form groups in maximum of five people to start a particular business.

He told them that "CDA did not fail you. You have acquired a lot of knowledge. Therefore, use the knowledge to build good businesses that would be profitable and sustainable. Be reminded that your business development plan will surely pass through the World Bank test for approval. So, build a business plan that can be funded and sustained."

Use the knowledge you acquired to build good businesses that would be profitable and sustainable. Be reminded that your business development plan will surely pass through the World Bank test for approval

CDA's FRESH FROM THE FARM

**CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE
BAYERO UNIVERSITY, KANO**

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